

Frequency of Depression Related Symptoms Among Undergraduate Medical Students

Dr. Syed Muhammad Kahal Haider (principle Author)

Kahalhaider8@gmail.com

Medical officer in Department of Anaesthesia and I.C.U in Ibn-E-Siena Hospital, Multan Medical And Dental College, (MMDC)

Dr. Zuha Ahmad (Author)

Zuhaahmedkhanmbbs@gmail.com

Samarkand State Medical University
House officer (MBBS)

Dr. Zain Iftikhar (Author)

Zainkhan3761@gmail.com

(MBBS) Medical Officer Cims, Multan

Dr. Hammad Hassan (Author)

Hammad88833@gmail.com

Ibn-e-Siena Hospital, Multan
House Officer (MBBS)

Dr. Khadeja Hashim (Author)

Khadejashim33@gmail.com

MCPS in Department of Anaesthesia and I.C.U in Ibn-E-Siena Hospital, Multan
Medical And Dental College, (MMDC)

Author Details

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Corresponding E-mail & Author*:

Dr. Syed M. Kahal Haider

Kahalhaider8@gmail.com

Medical Officer In
I.C.U In Ibn-E-Siena
Hospital, Multan
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Abstract

Introduction: Medical students are known to be the victims of tremendous stress. Yet its hard for all to see the sad face

behind the white coats. It is important for the medical educators to know the magnitude of depression symptoms and causing factors which not only effect their health and academic achievement but also has serious results as suicide .

Background: Psychological stress is common in medical colleges and associated with depression .Few studies are done concerning mental health of medical students .

Objectives: The objective of study was to assess the symptoms of depression among undergraduate medical students .

Methodology: A cross sectional was carried among the undergraduate medical students of Multan Medical and Dental College, Multan. Students were asked to complete

the questionnaire and then prevalence of depression was calculated .

Results: Symptoms of depression 67% were trouble with concentration, 68% shows tired ,64% had pessimistic thoughts.

Conclusion: The determinants identified in this study can be used in developing tailored interventions that effect depression using different promotion theories and models

Introduction

Everyone experiences sadness and unhappiness at some point in their lives. Clinical Depression, however, is more intense and of longer duration than typical sadness or grief, which interferes with a person's ability to engage in daily activities. The symptoms of depression can include: loss of interest or pleasure in previously enjoyable activities, major changes in appetite (either significantly reduced or increased), sleep problems (sleeping too much or too little), fatigue, a feeling of worthlessness or hopelessness, problems with concentration and making decisions, and thoughts of suicide.

There are two main types of depression, major depression and dysthymic disorder. A person diagnosed with Major Depression has experienced the previously mentioned symptoms for longer than 2 weeks. These symptoms either can occur repeatedly or only once; but they are typically severe. A

Dysthymia diagnosis means that depressive symptoms are less severe, and they have been present for at least 2 years on more days than not.

Individuals with bipolar disorder also display symptoms of depression. Bipolar disorder is a severe illness in which moods swing between 'up' states and 'down' states. A person in the 'down' state of bipolar disorder experiences one or more of the depressive symptoms mentioned previously.

Medical students are known to be the victims of tremendous mental stress. Yet it's hard for all to see the sad faces behind white coats. Medical students have to face multiple psychological changes in transformation from young careless students to an efficient doctor.

The personal and social sacrifice they have to make in order to maintain a good academic results in highly competitive environment put them under a lot of stress.

Depressive disorders are leading cause of disability worldwide. Studies suggest that most Common Mental Disorders have their first onset before the age of 24 . Anxiety and mood disorders are highly prevalent among young people aged 18–29 years. Almost 40% of young people experience their first episode of depression before the age of 20, with an average age of onset in the mid-20s . These years are most important for education, employment and social relationships.

Over the last decade, there has been growing interest in the mental health of university students. Globally, 24 to 34% university students experience depressive symptoms . Depressive disorders are one of the major causes of years lost due to disability and Disability Adjusted Life Years in young people

Occurrence of depression during the critical period of transition from adolescence to adulthood may have adverse effects, not only on development and academic functioning, but also on future employment and work

productivity. Studies have shown that depression leads to early attrition from university and poor academic performance . Moreover, depression is associated with lower employment prospects and unstable employment in adulthood .

Pakistan is one of the youngest countries in the region, with almost 30% population between 15 to 29 years of age. In addition to having limited resources to invest in education and health, Pakistan has witnessed some major crises over the last two decades. The country was hit by a major earthquake in 2005 and heavy floods in 2010 and 2022. A long wave of

terrorism and militancy (2000–2014) did not even spare schools and colleges. More than 100 children were dead in a terrorists attack on Army public school Peshawar in 2014-

the highest death toll in a single terrorist attack in the world. In 2016, a university in north-west province was attacked by terrorists, resulting in deaths of 19 students and teachers.

In Pakistan, a whole generation has grown up in an uncertain and insecure environment. Almost 70% population lives in rural areas. Meanwhile, over the last 20 years, trend of enrollment in higher education institutes has increased substantially with 10–15% of the eligible age group of 18–24 in universities or professional colleges. Even from less privileged areas, young people are getting higher education. Most of these people are from the first generation of their families to receive higher education.

With almost non-existent career counseling and mental health services at campuses, university students in Pakistan battle with a highly competitive environment, financial constraints, future uncertainty and parental and societal demands to excel in studies and secure good jobs. All these stressors put university students at high risk of developing common mental health problems particularly depression. For a developing country like Pakistan, health and well-being of its youth is of utmost importance as they are the future human capital.

Previous studies have shown fairly high level of distress, such as symptoms of depression among undergraduate medical students. In recent few years depression is the major cause of morbidity and suicidal attempts by the depressed medical students. It is important for medical educators to know the magnitude of depression symptoms in students and causing factors, which not only affect their health and academic achievement but also has serious consequences as suicide.

There is a need for reliable estimates of prevalence of mental health problems among medical students to design interventions tailored to specific needs of youth in Pakistan. Present study aims to conduct systematic review and meta analysis on prevalence of depression symptoms among undergraduate medical students in Pakistan.

We carried a 14 questionnaire based cross sectional study to find out the symptoms of depression among undergraduate medical students.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design:

Cross sectional study.

Study Area:

Multan Medical And Dental College, Multan (MMDC)

Study population :

Students of first year and second year MBBS.

Duration of study: One month (5/9 to 5/10/2022)

Sample Size:

80

Inclusion criteria :

First year and second year MBBS students.

Exclusion criteria : Unwilling students. Tools of data collection :

Questionnaire was designed to get relevant information.

Data Analysis:

Data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS 22

Results

The study results showed that total study population was **70**. Table **1** showed that **66%** students have

trouble with their concentration while reading. Table **2** showed **47%** students are facing memory issues.

Table **3** showed that **68%** students felt tired. Table **4** showed that **25%** of students have physical

Concentration Issue

Frequency Distribution of Students having Complaint of Headache, Stress and other Physical System

Remarks	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Yes	19	25%	19	25%
No	57	75%	76	100%

Frequency Distribution of Students having Negative Thoughts

Remarks	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Yes	49	64%	49	64%
No	27	36%	76	100%

Total 76 100%

Frequency Distribution of Students preferring Staying at Home all time				
Remarks	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Yes	54	71%	54	71%
No	22	29%	76	100%

Total **76** **100%**

Total 76 100%

Frequency Distribution of Students having Suicidal thoughts				
Remarks	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent

Yes	10	13%	10	13%
No	66	87%	76	100%

Total 76 100%

Frequency Distribution of Students having Difficulty to Enjoy Life				
Remarks	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent

Yes	34	45%	34	45%
No	42	55%	76	100%
Total		76 100%		

Frequency Distribution of Students Feeling Study Pressure				
Remarks	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percent

Yes	59	78%	59	78%
No	17	22%	76	100%
Total		76 100%		

Discussion

Our study confirmed that it is common tendency among under graduate that they face trouble while keeping mind on things they are reading i.e our study show that 66% students faced trouble and suffer from this condition. But on comparison depression among graduates in Jordan face depression by 50% due to certain factors like type of personality alcoholic, drug addicts, family history, pessimistic attitude⁸. Like our investigation it is seen that physical symptoms like stress and headache have been shown to an extent of 25% but on comparison the study of student in Bagalkot 133 under graduate student from 1st grad

College where included based on universal sampling method. Similarly in our study one more manifestation has been shown that helpless student %age is 53% due to low self esteem, fear, anxiety no motivation and it reaching the stage of burn out.

But on comparison int J Adv medical science 2020 shows that %age of helplessness is 27 % to 73%⁹.

In another case it has been shown that suicidal thoughts among under graduate is 13% due to low academic performance, dramatic mood swings withdrawal from friends or family talking or thinking about death but on comparison in Bangla Dash study published on 30th

July 2022, 38.8 % participant have suicidal ideation due to burn out stage. Student facing financial problems is one of the causes of depression in our study 13% students are effected due to large family and because they crowd out the brain ability to focus on long term ability. But on comparison in a survey of 3000 UK students 3 in 5 reported that they are worried about paying their loan and 80% worried not being able to cover their living expenses. The solution

to this problem is proper ergonomics, the deliver briefly psychosocial intervention and counseling to prevent students from depression¹⁰.

Limitations and Suggestions:

Our study was limited to the first year and second year MBBS students . • In Pakistan, the qualitative research is still not a common research

method. Its needed that qualitative research should be promoted in our country.

The results of this qualitative research study cannot be generalized because of the small

sample size.

A very limited number of studies were done in our country on this topic consequently very limited literature existed on this topic.

The sample in this study was only collected from the Multan Medical and Dental College, Multan that may restrict the findings. The sample might be extended to other provinces and cities of the country for gathering rich information about the symptoms of depression among undergraduate medical students .

Conclusion

The results of our study highlights some important factors that affect the initiation and control of depression among students of medical colleges .

These factors are categorized as financial problems ,pessimistic thoughts, headache , stress and other physical symptoms .Government and private medical colleges should consider social norms .The

determinants identified in this study can be used in developing tailored interventions that effect

depression using different promotion theories and models .For example progressive muscle relaxation that can increase the effectiveness of depression relieving programs at different individual levels .Counselling and regular physical activities could help to compensate the depression symptoms prevalence among undergraduate medical students .

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